

RTM PROCESSING OF HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Resin transfer moulding (RTM) has a high potential for the cost effective manufacture of net-shaped structures of continuous fibre reinforced polymer composites. The future application in primary structures requires the reliable processing of resins which polycondense during curing, resulting typically in a high release of gaseous products. The basic approach of this paper was directed towards the development of a technique applying a condensation-like polymer and fibre preforms of carbon, ceramic and quartz fibres with high fibre volume contents of 50 to 65 %, resulting in void-free composites which are competitive to autoclave processed parts. A RTM process has been established which allows the infiltration of fabrics of nearly any shape and contour. Processing details as well as mechanical properties which have been evaluated at temperatures up to 300° C are described.

KEYWORDS: resin transfer moulding, viscosity, polycondensation, polystyrylpyridine, 2D-fibre architecture, permeability

INTRODUCTION

The resin transfer moulding process is a well known technique for the injection of a liquid thermosetting resin matrix into a closed mould containing a positioned fibre preform of continuous fibres. Principally, the RTM technique is one of the most promising manufacturing processes for high performance composites with respect to costs, as expensive raw materials like prepregs are not necessary. Additionally, the process can be principally fully automatized e.g. by cutting the preforms with water jet or by stacking the preforms with roboters into the moulds. In the past, many investigations have been conducted concerning numeric modelling and simulations of the RTM process and manufacturing of prototypes. For that, specifically fabrics with low flow resistance and one-part epoxy resin systems, specially adapted to RTM conditions, have been developed [1,2].

Nevertheless, to compete with other composite manufacturing routes and to enter the civil engineering market with composite primary structures, high fibre volume fractions of more than 50 % of commercially available fabrics must be achieved via RTM. Additionally, high temperature matrix systems, often cured via a polycondensation reaction, must be available as resins of low viscosity. Resins, which polycondense during curing, result typically in a high release of gaseous products, which consequently lead to a more or less porous matrix when processing in a closed mould, resulting in poor mechanical properties.

In this study, the resin polystyrylpyridine (PSP) has been chosen to establish a RTM technique which should solve these problems exemplarily and, demonstrate that high performance composites with nearly void-free matrices and high fibre volume contents can be fabricated reproducibly. PSP resin, prepared from the polycondensation reaction of a methylated pyridine and aromatic dialdehyde, was originally developed by the French company SNPE and modified by Dow Chemical [3,4]. This commercially available polymer exhibits excellent thermomechanical properties and very good flame resistance but failed to attract widespread commercial application because it requires a long cure schedule and evolves volatiles during the polycondensation curing. Nevertheless, this one-part polymer is an attractive candidate as a matrix system for structures of aero-engines and aircrafts.

MATERIAL DESCRIPTION AND MOULD DESIGN

Generally, the resin's viscosity should be as low as possible when infiltrating the highly packed array of fibres in the mould. This is desirable since high injection pressures may cause mould deformation or fibre wash-out, i.e. the reinforcement is washed away from its original position. The mould should be heated to a temperature where the resin reaches the desired viscosity. This is not necessarily the lowest possible one, since higher temperatures not only reduce the viscosity but also reduce the time of gelation. The key point for infiltration is therefore to determine a mould temperature providing a viscosity as low as possible without causing premature gelation. During curing, polycondensation-like resins form volatile by-products like vapour which may lead to a high content of voids in the finished composites. As a consequence, the curing pressure must be beyond the vapour pressure, resulting in stiff and tight moulds of steel.

At room temperature, neat PSP resins are solid with a density of 1.14 g/cm^3 . When increasing the temperature, the viscosity of the resin decreases drastically and reaches the lowest value of about 15 mPas at 200°C . The time remaining at this viscosity amounts to 30 minutes which seems to be sufficient for the infiltration of even large and complex shaped reinforcements.

Figure 1: Viscosity of PSP resin at constant temperatures after heating-up with 2 K/min

Nevertheless, lower levels of constant temperatures combined with a higher viscosity increase the time of injection considerably (Fig. 1). As a good compromise between low viscosity and long infiltration time, a infiltration temperature of 170° C was chosen for all studies.

Commercial 2D-fabrics of carbon, ceramic and quartz fibres have been used as reinforcement (Table 1). The carbon fibres were evaluated in all common modifications of high tenacity (HT), intermediate modulus (IM) and high modulus (HM), representing typical reinforcements for structural CFRP components. Ceramic and quartz fabrics were investigated with three different types of fibres as possible reinforcements for composites with more functional properties, i.e. in radome applications. The number of filaments, the fibre radii and the areal weight in terms of gram per m² differ considerably for all materials. As a result, a variable number of fabric layers were necessary to keep the fibre volume contents relatively constant in the mould.

Table 1: Typical data of woven fabrics used as reinforcements

Material	Fibre Type	Weaving Mode	Filament Number	Fibre Radius [µm]	Areal Weight [g/m ²]	Fibre Density [g/cm ³]
Carbon	Akzo HTA	Plain	3000	3.5	245	1.76
	Toray T800	Plain	6000	2.5	270	1.81
	Toray M40	Twill 2/2	3000	3.25	200	1.81
Ceramic	Nicalon NL 207	Plain	500	7	275	2.55
	Ube Tyranno Lox M	Plain	1600	5	260	2.37
Quartz	Ciba Lyvertex 20766	8 H Satin	68	7.5	290	2.32

A composite panel size of 300 x 300 x 3 mm³ was selected to be suitable for principal investigations. An injection mould has been manufactured, designed as a two-chamber mould with an integrated reservoir for heating-up the resin as well as the fibres simultaneously before infiltration. The RTM mould was fabricated out of a steel alloy to ensure durability and to allow high internal pressures without any essential deformations. To protect the steel against acid agents while curing, the mould was coated with chromium as a corrosion-resistant surface coating. The mould was tightened with plates and covered with electric cartridge heat elements and insulation packages of glass felts to ensure a homogeneous temperature distribution within the total mould. A cross-view of the RTM-mould is depicted in Fig. 2, showing the basic elements of this injection tool.

For impregnation, the dry preform of fibre reinforcement was arranged into the fibre chamber, whereas the solid resin was placed into the resin chamber, both connected by a tubular channel. After closing the mould the total arrangement was set up vertically as shown in Fig. 2. Two valves, each on the top of the two chambers, ensured the flow of the resin into the fibre chamber after reaching the infiltration temperature. The valve in the resin chamber was connected with a tank of pressured nitrogen to facilitate the injection as well as to apply the necessary pressure while curing. The ventilation port at the rear side of the fibre chamber was connected with a vacuum pump to evacuate air and volatiles before and during infiltration.

Figure 2: Two-chamber RTM-mould

- | | |
|---------------|--------------------|
| 1 Gas inlet | 4 Resin chamber |
| 2 Steel frame | 5 Fibre chamber |
| 3 Sealing | 6 Ventilation port |

As the resin was embedded before melting and as the mould was hermetically gas tight except the valves, any exposure of workers to chemicals and toxic volatiles could be excluded. This was one essential goal of the mould design ensuring a high process safety and acceptance for a future usage as a medium to high volume production facility.

PROCESSING PARAMETERS

The resin flow through a three dimensional fibrous preform can be described by Darcy's law in vectorial form :

$$\underline{V} = -\frac{1}{\eta} \cdot \underline{K} \cdot \nabla p \quad (1)$$

where η is the viscosity, p the pressure, \underline{V} the infiltration velocity and \underline{K} the tensor of permeability. If one considers the vertical position of the mould and assumes a horizontal resin front, which is constant over the preform's thickness, the infiltration kinetics can be written one-dimensional as

$$V = -\frac{1}{\eta} \cdot \frac{k}{L} \cdot \Delta p \quad (2)$$

where L is the length of the preform and k the permeability in the direction of infiltration. The macroscopic flow in the mould is governed mainly by the geometry of the fibre architecture, i.e. by the fibre volume content Φ and the fibre radius r [5,6]. The permeability k can then be expressed by the formulation of Carman and Kozeny

$$k = \frac{r^2}{4 \cdot K_z} \left(\frac{(1-\phi)^3}{\phi^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

with K_z as the Kozeny constant.

This equation indicates for example that for fibre contents of 100 % or for infinitively small fibres, respectively, the permeability leads theoretically to zero. Vice versa, the infiltration velocity increases with thicker fibres and lower fibre volume contents. Practically this means that fibre preforms made of T800 fibres show half of the infiltration velocity of HTA preforms with the same fibre content, because of their by 30 % thinner fibre radius (see Table 1).

To validate the theory, a number of tests have been conducted. In several pre-tests the permeability constant k has been determined experimentally for carbon fabrics. With HTA plain woven fabrics of 61 % fibre content, k amounts to $1.63 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$, corresponding to a Kozeny constant K_z of

$$K_z = 0.03$$

Assuming, that this is a material constant for this kind of preform and mould, the dependance of k on fibre radius r and fibre volume content ϕ can be determined according to equation (3). Fig. 3 shows this relationship for technical relevant values of r and ϕ in general.

Figure 3: Relationship between permeability and fibre volume content and fibre radius, respectively, for HTA carbon preforms

With these results, an estimation of a suitable RTM cycle in terms of pressure difference Δp and the infiltration time t for a complete preform impregnation can be conducted. By transformation of equation (2) one obtains the equation for the pressure difference between the two ends of the preform

$$\Delta p = \frac{L^2 \cdot \eta}{2 \cdot k \cdot t} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 4 shows graphically for three distinct viscosities, that low pressures below 1 bar can only be achieved with long infiltration times of up to 30 minutes for HTA preforms of the required impregnation length of 300 mm. Considerably faster impregnations within 10 minutes are possible with preforms of fibre contents lower than 60 % and applied pressures up to 10 bar.

Figure 4: Required pressure difference Δp vs infiltration time t for the impregnation of HTA carbon fibre preform of 300 mm in length

These calculations and the rheological properties of PSP resin lead to a RTM manufacturing cycle which has been standardized for all investigations, i.e. each fabric was infiltrated with the same process parameters. Generally, this process can be divided into four major steps:

- Melting of the resin in the heated mould,
- Infiltration of the preform at 170° C under low pressure,
- Degassing of condensates between 170° C and 208° C,
- Polymerisation under high pressure (21 bar).

Prior to infiltration, woven fabrics were cut to size and reliably stacked into the fibre chamber to obtain controlled fibre volume contents of 50-65 %. Orthotropic as well as quasi-isotropic lay-ups have been examined. After sealing and closing the mould, both chambers were heated up simultaneously with a rate of 2 K/min up to 170° C without any pressure. The duration of infiltration depended on the permeability of the fabric and the applied pressure difference, which was determined from the process simulation parameters. In all cases, the mould temperature increased after 30 minutes with a heating rate of 0.5 K/min up to the curing temperature of 208° C. During this period, the ventilation port of the fibre chamber was open to allow volatiles to escape. Polymerisation was conducted at 21 bar, i.e. beyond the vapour pressure of water at this temperature. The composite panels were cured for 8 hours at 208° C within the mould. After cooling they were removed from the mould and partly post-cured in

an oven at 240° C for 8 hours. Fig. 5 shows the main steps of the selected RTM cycle in combination with the curve of the resin's viscosity.

Figure 5: Manufacturing cycle for the resin transfer moulding of PSP resin into woven fabrics

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

After curing and post-curing, respectively, the microstructure of the composites has been examined by SEM microscopy. Typically, only cured samples showed a matrix which is nearly free of voids and encloses the fibre filaments with a high degree of regularity (Fig. 6).

The open porosity, measured via water absorption by the Archimedes method, lay in the range of 1 %, corresponding to a density of ca. 1.50 g/cm³ for carbon fibres, 1.65 g/cm³ for the SiO₂-quartz fibre reinforcements and 1.75 g/cm³ for the composites reinforced with ceramic fibres.

After post-curing, a certain amount of transversal cracks occurred in the matrix, due to the mismatch of thermal elongations between fibres and the relatively brittle matrix. As a result, the open porosity was measured to be twice the one of the non-treated samples.

Mechanical tests have been conducted at temperatures up to 300° C to evaluate the thermal stability of the composites. In place of all fibre variations, only carbon fibre reinforced composites will be described in the following. All post-cured samples showed relatively constant levels over the temperature concerning short beam strength with the lowest values for HM fibres (Fig. 7). The post-curing treatment led to a strong and stable bonding between the carbon fibres and the matrix, even at high temperatures.

Figure 6: SEM micrograph (100 x) of a CFRP composite with 57 % fibre volume content.

Figure 7: Interlaminar shear strength vs testing temperature of CFRP composites before and after post-curing at 240° C / 8 h

In contrast, only the cured samples showed a high degree of dependence on test temperature and fibre type. Differing widely at room temperature, all ILSS values at 300° C were far below the strength levels of post-cured materials at the same temperature indicating the necessity of the post-cure step after curing to get a composite of high thermal stability.

Additionally, plates with thicknesses of 1 to 30 mm (Fig. 8) as well as thin walled tubes of 300 mm length have been fabricated in similar moulds with the same RTM process. First prototypes with complex geometries like blades and vanes have been realized for demonstration purposes and have shown the feasibility of this RTM technology for the manufacture of high performance components in principal.

Figure 8: Examples of CFRP plates with various thicknesses, manufactured via RTM

CONCLUSIONS

A process for resin transfer moulding has been established using commercially available 2D-fibre fabrics and polystyrylpyridine resins. Carbon, quartz as well as ceramic fibres have been embedded in a mould of steel and impregnated with a RTM cycle, derived from numeric simulation models based on Darcy's law. A suitable design of the mould as the most critical step to achieve homogeneous and thermal stable matrices via condensation-like resins has been realised. Despite of the relatively long processing times and the still labour intensive manufacture, a RTM equipment is now available which allows the near-net shape fabrication of components with high fibre contents. These investigations demonstrated the suitability of the RTM technology for high performance composites in advanced aerospace and automotive structures.

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